

Unification for Gravity and Electromagnetic Field in Kerr Newman Solution

Sangwha-Yi*

Department of Math , Taejon University 300-716 , South Korea

*Corresponding Author: Sangwha-Yi, Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

Abstract: Solutions of unified theory equations of gravity and electromagnetism has to satisfy Einstein-Maxwell equation. Specially, solution of the unified theory is generally Kerr-Newman solution in vacuum. We finally found the revised Einstein gravity tensor equation with new term (2-order contravariant metric tensor two times product and the constant matrix) is right in Kerr-Newman solution.

Keywords: General relativity theory, Unified Theory; Kerr-Newman solution; 2-order contravariant metric tensor two times product; The constant matrix

PACS Number: 04,04.90.+e,41.12

1. INTRODUCTION

This theory's aim is that we discover the revised Einstein gravity equation had Kerr-Newman solution in vacuum.

First, we know the revised Einstein gravity equation[1].

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}I(g^{\theta\theta})^2 = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$$

In this time,

$$\Lambda = k \frac{GQ^2}{c^4}, I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

If Eq(1) take covariant differential operator,

$$(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)_{;\mu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}I_2 g^{\theta\theta} g^{\theta\theta}_{;\mu} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu;\mu} = 0 \quad (2-i)$$

$$(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)_{;\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}I_2 g^{\theta\theta} g^{\theta\theta}_{;\nu} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu;\nu} = 0 \quad (2-ii)$$

In this time, in Kerr-Newman solution

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\theta\theta} &= 1/g^{\theta\theta} = \rho^2 = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta \\ g^{\theta\theta}_{;\rho} &= \frac{\partial g^{\theta\theta}}{\partial x^\rho} + 2\Gamma^{\theta}_{\sigma\rho} g^{\sigma\theta} = \frac{\partial g^{\theta\theta}}{\partial r} + 2\Gamma^{\theta}_{0r} g^{\theta\theta} \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2} \right) + 2 \cdot \frac{r}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho^2} = -2 \frac{1}{\rho^3} \cdot \frac{r}{\rho} + \frac{2r}{\rho^4} = 0 \\ g^{\theta\theta}_{;\theta} &= \frac{\partial g^{\theta\theta}}{\partial x^\theta} + 2\Gamma^{\theta}_{\sigma\theta} g^{\sigma\theta} = \frac{\partial g^{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} + 2\Gamma^{\theta}_{\theta\theta} g^{\theta\theta} \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2} \right) - 2 \cdot \frac{1}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{2a^2}{\rho} \cos \theta \sin \theta \cdot \frac{1}{\rho^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$= -2 \cdot \frac{1}{\rho^3} \cdot -\frac{2a^2 \cos\theta \sin\theta}{\rho} - \frac{4a^2}{\rho^4} \cos\theta \sin\theta = 0 \quad (4)$$

If $g^{\theta\theta}_{;\rho} = V_\rho$, the vector transformation is

$$0 = V_\rho = \frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial x^\rho} V'_\alpha, \quad V'_\alpha = 0 \quad (5)$$

Therefore, if the coordinate is not the Kerr-Newman's coordinate, the covariant differential of

$$g^{\theta\theta} = \frac{1}{\rho^2} \text{ is still zero in the changed coordinates.}$$

2. THE REVISED EINSTEIN GRAVITY EQUATION AND KERR-NEWMAN SOLUTION

In this theory, Eq(1) can change the following equation.

$$R_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} (T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T^\lambda{}_\lambda) + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} I(g^{\theta\theta})^2 \quad (6)$$

In this time, in vacuum, specially, in Kerr-Newman solution,

$$T_{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad T^\lambda{}_\lambda = g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} \neq 0 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, Eq(1) is

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad -\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} I(g^{\theta\theta})^2 &= R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{2G}{c^5} (F_{\mu\rho} F_{\nu}{}^\rho - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma}) \\ &= \frac{2G}{c^5} (g_{\mu\nu} F_{\nu\rho} F^{\nu\rho} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In this time, According to [2],

$$\begin{aligned} E = F_{01} = -F_{10} &= \frac{Q (r^2 - a^2 \cos^2 \theta)}{(r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta)^2} = \frac{Q (r^2 - a^2 \cos^2 \theta)}{\rho^4} \\ B = F_{23} = -F_{32} &= \frac{2Q \arccos \theta}{(r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta)^2} = \frac{2Q \arccos \theta}{\rho^4} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{2G}{c^5} (g_{\mu\nu} F_{\nu\rho} F^{\nu\rho} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma}) \\ &= -\frac{G}{c^5} g_{\mu\nu} I(B^2 + E^2), \quad I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= -\frac{G}{c^5} \begin{pmatrix} g_{00} & 0 & 0 & -g_{03} \\ 0 & g_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -g_{22} & 0 \\ g_{30} & 0 & 0 & -g_{33} \end{pmatrix} (B^2 + E^2), \quad B^2 + E^2 = \frac{Q^2}{\rho^4} \\ &= -\frac{G}{c^5} \begin{pmatrix} g_{00} & 0 & 0 & -g_{03} \\ 0 & g_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -g_{22} & 0 \\ g_{30} & 0 & 0 & -g_{33} \end{pmatrix} \frac{Q^2}{\rho^4} = -\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} I(g^{\theta\theta})^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Lambda = k \frac{GQ^2}{c^4} \quad (10)$$

3. CONCLUSION

We finally found the revised Einstein equation of unified theory (the gravity and electromagnetic field) is right in Kerr-Newman solution.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.Yi, "Unified Theory of Gravity and Electromagnetic Field in Reissner-Nodstrom Solution, Kerr-Newman Solution", *6*,11(2019),pp1-3
- [2] K.Rosquist, "Interacting Kerr-Newman Fields", International Center for Relativistic Astrophysics, MG12,Paris (2009)
- [3] S.Yi, "Spherical Solution of Classical Quantum Gravity", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science, *6*,8,(2019),pp3-6
- [4] S.Weinberg, Gravitation and Cosmology(John wiley & Sons,Inc,1972)
- [5] P.Bergman, Introduction to the Theory of Relativity(Dover Pub. Co.,Inc., New York,1976),Chapter V
- [6] C.Misner, K,Thorne and J. Wheeler, Gravitation(W.H.Freedman & Co.,1973)
- [7] S.Hawking and G. Ellis, The Large Scale Structure of Space-Time(Cam-bridge University Press,1973)
- [8] R.Adler,M.Bazin and M.Schiffer, Introduction to General Relativity(McGraw-Hill,Inc.,1965)

Citation: Sangwha-Yi, (2019). Unification for Gravity and Electromagnetic Field in Kerr-Newman Solution. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science (IJARPS)* 6(12), pp.11-13, 2019.

Copyright: © 2019 Authors, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Page 13